
Perimeter security utilizing thermal object detection

Georgios Orfanidis^{1*}, Konstantinos Ioannidis^{2*}, Stefanos Vrochidis³ and Ioannis Kompatsiaris⁴

¹ Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH, GR 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece;

g.orfanidis@iti.gr

² Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH, GR 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece; kioan-

nid@iti.gr

³ Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH, GR 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece;

stefanos@iti.gr

⁴ Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH, GR 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece;

ikom@iti.gr

* Correspondence: GO g.orfanidis@iti.gr; KI kioannid@iti.gr

Highlights

What are the main findings?

- Thermal object detection increases surveillance capabilities.
- Deploying a thermal surveillance system is a practical and economical solution.

What is the implication of the main finding?

- Thermal detection can be a great complementary to other surveillance system.
- More thermal detection systems can be utilized.

Abstract

In recent years there has been observed an increasing interest in artificial intelligence applications, in a widespread spectrum of fields which include among others, robotics, communications, artistic creations, security and protection technologies etc. Of the latter categories, one field which has benefitted largely is surveillance and security technologies. This fact is combined with an increase in omnipresent automatic surveillance systems installations which paves the way to new technologies. Technologies that are being promoted are the ones offering uninterrupted, robust, efficient and reliable operation. In this work we examine the ability of thermal automatic detection systems to fulfill their role as essential part of such mechanism. The primary advantage of thermal detection is the potential to provide a 24-hour uninterrupted detection service exploiting its innate robustness against environmental or weather changes and shifts in illumination conditions. For providing a reliable security mechanism a second requirement is considered sine qua non; the efficiency of the system in order to provide timely alerts for potential threats and incidents. In this work we evaluate various efficient object detection models operating solely in thermal/infra-red spectrum to examine their role as potential backbone detectors in surveillance systems.

Keywords: Critical infrastructure, object detection, surveillance, thermal, Infrared

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1. Introduction

Object detection is one of the fundamental tasks in computer vision. Nevertheless, the introduction of Deep learning techniques and more specifically Convolutional Neural Networks in recent years has leveraged the performance of the relevant models to unprecedented levels. The latter fact has permitted the introduction of detection tech-

43 niques in various automated solution for surveillance and security purposes. Addition-
44 ally, although the primary field to apply such monitoring systems is the visual spectrum
45 (RGB) there are multiple cases where this obvious selection proved Insufficient. The
46 performance of detection systems operating in visual spectrum has reached impressive
47 levels of performance since the introduction of the early stages of Deep learning tech-
48 niques. Pioneer works include Faster RCNN [1], Single Shot Detector (SSD) [2] an inno-
49 vative single-step network and You Only Look Once (Yolo) an efficient oriented model
50 [3]. Those works are based on Convolutional Neural Networks which tend to dominate
51 the detection field. Nevertheless, other approaches also exist, which utilize different ar-
52 chitectures like Transformer. Carion in [4] provided an end-to-end architecture to train a
53 transformer and provide a detection model. In general the works are focusing on im-
54 proving the detection ability while simultaneously providing swift models with in-
55 creased usability.

56 In fair weather and illumination conditions the performance of those detection sys-
57 tems is unparalleled to none [5]. On the other hand, when the conditions are not thus
58 favourable the detection ability diminishes significantly. At those conditions a comple-
59 mentary system is useful to provide detections. Missing objects due to low visibility is
60 unacceptable for robust protection systems and in this case thermal object detection is
61 utilized. The latter provide decent detecting capability in harsh weather and illumination
62 conditions. To further elaborate, harsh conditions might include foggy, misty or rainy
63 weather, low visibility might also include dawn, sunset or heavily cloudy weather etc.
64 [5]. In practice thermal object can operate under a large range of climatic conditions, in-
65 cluding fair, cloudy, dawn, misty, rainy and foggy weather with minimal impact on its
66 detection ability. This feature is unique compared to other visual detections. Addition-
67 ally, specifically the thermal cameras can operate without any external "light" source by
68 detecting the thermal radiation of each object, which provides an affordable alternative to
69 the installation of multiple light sources to illuminate the whole area around the moni-
70 tored area [5]. Finally, another advantage of the thermal detection is the smaller image
71 resolution of the cameras along with the single-channel processing which can boost the
72 processing time of the system.

73 Due to the increased interest of the community, a large number of datasets specifi-
74 cally created has been published and utilized to promote the research on the generic ob-
75 ject detection field. This has aimed the comparison of works and the progress in the field.
76 Datasets such as Common objects in context (Coco) [6] operate as benchmark dataset for
77 this purpose. On the thermal spectrum, unfortunately, there isn't any massive dataset
78 which could uptake this role. In a research over the datasets being utilized in thermal
79 detections almost 3 out of 4 works were reporting results in non-publicly available da-
80 taset [7].

81 For the purpose of this work public datasets were utilised which included thermal
82 images as the intention is to validate the credibility of thermal detectors as security tools.
83 In order to provide an application easily maintainable, and constructible the focus was
84 only on public datasets. Certain of the datasets contained also visual images but only the
85 thermal part of the dataset was utilised, as it is the case of FLIR-ADAS [8]. A certain issue
86 is the availability of objects of interest inside the public datasets. Within the aspect of this
87 work only the relevant to the surveillance purposes were kept and all others were dis-
88 carded. Similarly, we have annotated relevant objects in cases these were not available.
89 The relevant classes included persons, cars, trucks, buses, motorcycle, bicycle and fire.
90 The person class is essential for every surveillance task as it is obvious. Next 5 classes in-
91 clude the most commonly utilized vehicles and thus, they were considered indicative of
92 human presence and activity in the surveyed area. For this reason they were also in-
93 cluded in the relevant detectable classes. Finally fire instances constitute one of the major

94 threats for infrastructures, installations, building and persons, and thus, it was incorpo-
95 rated to the final classes of interest. Every instance of those objects was annotated in the
96 dataset being utilised.

97 Additionally, three different detection models were examined for the surveillance
98 task. Two of them were of the Yolo family, Yolov8 [9] and Yolov11 [10] while the 3rd one
99 was from the transformer doctrine but specifically focusing on efficiency Real Time Detr
100 (RT-Detr) [11]. The inclusion of three models permitted the research over the best per-
101 forming model under different parameters.

102 The main contributions of this paper are the research over the performance of effi-
103 cient real-time object detectors in the IR/thermal spectrum, in varying parameters and
104 model sizes. Additionally, the main question that this work attempts to answer is
105 whether the existing detection model can operate in a robust and reliable way in order to
106 constitute the backbone of a 24/7 thermal surveillance detection system.

107 This paper is organized as follows: an overview of related work is presented in the
108 following section. A small discussion of the unique features of IR/thermal radiation is
109 presented in Section 3. Section 4 discusses the datasets being utilised for this work, while
110 the next Section aggregates the parameters being applied, the actual results and their
111 impact in the model selection. Finally, the last Section, Section 6 concludes the paper and
112 summarises the main ideas deduced from it.

113 2. Related Work

114 This work utilizes a deep learning approach for detection purposes but deploys its
115 algorithm solely on thermal bandwidth, and thus, this section will summarize related
116 works in both of these fields. As mentioned in the Introduction, the emergence of deep
117 learning in the detection field has created many remarkable works. Initial approaches
118 focuses on achieving better results but as the advancements accumulated, a large portion
119 of the innovative works shifted its focus on promoting efficient yet effective models. A
120 major chapter on these efficient models is the Yolo tradition. This tradition has created a
121 whole series of detectors [12] which have as their primary focus to provide a model as
122 efficient as possible. Each subsequent Yolo version attempts to include some innovation
123 in the architecture while maintaining its fast processing ability [13].

124 The initial works also were almost exclusively based on Convolutional Neural
125 Networks. Further implementations introduced newer architecture like visual trans-
126 formers and a discussion commenced [14]. Nowadays the best performance is achieved
127 by visual transformers, yet they typically require many data, are slower and more re-
128 source consuming than their counterpart. Examples are implementations like Co-Detr
129 [15] which although achieves state-of-the-art performance in datasets like Coco, it failed
130 to provide a lightweight efficient model. A new generation of transformers attempted to
131 crack into the efficient models based on CNN employing efficient alternatives to achieve
132 real-time processing like the aforementioned RT-Detr.

133 Regarding the other field of interest of this paper, the thermal object detection, the
134 initial interest of the community focused primarily or even exclusively to human detec-
135 tion. Although the reason for focusing primarily or even exclusively on person monitor-
136 ing might be traced back in the pre-deep learning era where the inclusion of many classes
137 of interest was a really hard task to accomplish but there are other practical causes also.
138 The human presence per se is crucial and could provide valuable information and in-
139 crease the environmental awareness of the system. Nevertheless, detecting more classes
140 is typically more useful and can leverage the practical uses of the solution. A typical
141 example is [16] where the authors presented a system for thermal detection of person and
142 vehicles. This work is pre-deep learning and thus, it utilizes machine learning techniques.
143 Another attempt for thermal detection is presented in [17] where the authors utilize a

144 multi-camera surveillance system based on Yolov4 [18] model to monitor a crowd in in-
145 door places.

146 The authors of [5] created their own dataset to examine the thermal detection in
147 unfavorable weather conditions. The dataset included frames captured in clear, foggy
148 and rainy weather and primarily focused on detected persons in various positions (there
149 was a human vs non-human ---dog--- task included also), while the detectors where all
150 CNN based models. An example of multi-person localization via the use of a Thermopile
151 sensor is presented in [19] comparing Yolov5 [20] and Detr [5] algorithms. The results are
152 anonymous by nature due to low resolution of the sensor but on the other hand they lack
153 any clarity for visualization purposes.

154 In another work in [21] the authors utilized SSD with mobileNet v1 and v2 to detect
155 3 classes, car, bicycle, and person, on FLIR-ADAS dataset v1. The lack of IR/thermal ex-
156 tended datasets has resulted in attempts to transfer features from richer domain, as the
157 visual one, in works like [22], where pseudo-multimodal pairs are generated in order to
158 improve performance. Researchers often attempt to improve the performance of the de-
159 veloped applications especially to achieve real-time performance, as in [23], where the
160 authors focused on vehicles' detection in Infrared images utilizing a modified Yolov7
161 model [24].

162 One popular application for thermal object detection is Autonomous Driving. In [25]
163 the authors introduced a new VGG-based detector named TIRNet and focused on
164 providing an efficient system which was evaluated on a custom-compiled dataset named
165 CTIR and on KAIST dataset [26]. The dataset availability for the thermal spectrum is
166 apparent and in this field. For example, a new interesting visual dataset appears in [27]
167 which attempts to cover more diverse sceneries. One approach for taking advantage of
168 these datasets is to transfer knowledge from visual to thermal spectrum. For example, in
169 another work which also focuses on Autonomous Driving [28] it uses transfer learning to
170 provide low-level features transfer from visual to thermal domain in order to improve
171 the performance in low lighting conditions. The models uses were SSD and Faster
172 RCNN. Increasing the environmental awareness is crucial for Autonomous Driving and
173 the authors in [29], attempt in an innovative manner to enrich this knowledge by de-
174 tecting roadside wild animals utilizing thermal imagery and a Yolov8 variation. This
175 approach aims at employment in embedded systems in order to mitigate the chance of
176 animal-vehicle collision.

177 As stated before, typical resolution of thermal imagery is small and thus, deploy-
178 ment of thermal object detection models in embedded devices might seem reasonable.
179 Nevertheless, the detection of small objects in the latter already stretched resolution is
180 challenging, especially when combined with the innate scarcity of detailed textures for
181 thermal imagery. Applications which attempt to contribute to this task are always inter-
182 esting such as the case in [30], where the authors utilize a Yolov5 [20] based model de-
183 ployed in integrated circuits TIFAD [31]. The application datasets were mainly TIFAD
184 [32] and for model robustness evaluation HRSID [33]. The relevant works including
185 thermal object detection on embedded devices is even more limited and the ones pub-
186 lished attempt to fill in the vacuum in this research field by introducing model im-
187 provements, as in the case of [34] for a variation of Yolov3 [35] but the use of
188 non-benchmark datasets ultimately restricts the impact to the community.

189 Another application of thermal detection is for research and rescue operations, es-
190 pecially during nighttime. One such example is presented in [36] where the authors em-
191 ploy a thermal object detection mechanism to detect waterborne individuals during
192 nighttime where it is more challenging to accomplish. They also compiled a custom da-
193 taset to train and evaluate their model which was based on Yolov5 architecture [20].

194 As mentioned before, in the surveillance thermal object detection subtask, works
195 often focus on person detection like in [37], where the authors presents a method for
196 background removal and is applied on 2 sequences of the CDNet-2014 dataset [38]. De-
197 pending on the problem to be solved the classes of interest might include more objects,
198 like in [39] which attempts to detect animals in thermal imagery as it consider them a
199 threat for corps and farmers especially during the night. Due to object instance sparsity a
200 GAN, more specifically ThermalGAN [40], has been utilised to increase the number of
201 training samples while the selected model was Yolov4. Other works attempt to unify the
202 visual and thermal detection subtasks, considering they are complementary to each oth-
203 er. In [41], three classes were detected animals, people and vehicles while the model be-
204 ing utilized was Yolov3 [35] and the focus was the development of an outdoor surveil-
205 lance system. A related task for mitigating potential threats is detecting UAVs utilizing
206 thermal imagery [42]. The authors in the latter publication evaluated 4 models, and more
207 specifically Yolov9 [43], GELAN [44], DETR and ViTDet [45] in the anti-UAV Dataset
208 compiled during the 2023 CVPR [46]. The best performance (in mAP) was achieved by
209 GELAN while the faster detector was Yolov9.

210 As it is obvious by the literature, the thermal object detection field is deprived of the
211 rich, extended benchmark datasets available in the visual object detection. On the other
212 hand, shutting down the entire department of thermal detections deprive any system
213 from the advantages of the thermal spectrum. Thus, many researchers focused on lever-
214 aging both spectrums to their advantage. One such work, which aims at providing a
215 light-weight yet effective multi-modal fusion model is [47]. The main mechanism utilized
216 contains channel switching and spatial attention (CSSA) while the evaluation was per-
217 formed in FLIR and LLVIP [48] datasets. Another multimodal system [49] perform late
218 fusion to the detections from different modalities while applying a simple probabilistic
219 ensembling approach to enhance the scores of consensual detections. Due to its late fu-
220 sion nature, it can be applied to both align as well unaligned multimodal datasets. An
221 interesting network which further expands the multimodality and encompasses 3 mo-
222 dalities in a Confluent Triple-Flow Network is presented in [50]. The focus of the paper is
223 to locate salient objects by utilizing 3 flows: a visual, a thermal and a complementary one
224 containing information from both latter flows utilizing a divide-and-conquer approach to
225 independently process each flow while simultaneously extracting complementary fea-
226 tures. Finally, they employ their own compiled dataset VT-IMAG to evaluate the per-
227 formance of their mechanism.

228 3. IR-Thermal radiation

229 Infrared (IR and sometimes also called infrared light) is an electromagnetic radiation
230 (EMR) which has wavelengths longer than visible light but shorter than microwaves. Its
231 name denotes that it is under (infra) the red band of the visual spectrum which is the
232 nearest to IR. There is no strict definition of the boundaries of the IR band but it is
233 roughly between 780 nm to 1 mm wavelengths. It is not visible by the human eye yet it
234 transfers or reflects heat. The IR band is divided into an active IR band and a thermal
235 (passive) IR band [51]. The active band covers the part near the visual spectrum
236 (0.7-2.5 μ m) and it is divided into the NIR (near infrared) and the SWIR (shortwave in-
237 frared) spectrum. The SWIR has slightly better performance when low levels of obscur-
238 ants like fog and smoke are present. The passive IR band on the other hand covers spectra
239 most distant to the visual band. It is divided into the Mid-Wave (MWIR) and the
240 Long-Wave InfraRed (LWIR) band. Both bands are capable of capturing the emission of
241 heat radiation from monitored subjects but MWIR also pertain some reflective properties,
242 whereas LWIR comprises almost entirely of emitted radiation [51]. In practice the dif-
243 ference between the active (reflected IR radiation) and passive (thermal IR radiation) is

244 the ability for the latter to operate without the requirement of an external source of light
245 or heat (which would be reflected by the object's surface) and thus, are highly robust to
246 illumination fluctuations and weather conditions while can be fully functional in the
247 darkness [52]. The authors in [53] employ three modalities, and more specifically, visual,
248 thermal and Lidar input, to perform 3D object detection and eliminate blind spots for
249 navigation purposes. The detector employs a Swin Transformer [54] to cope with the
250 detection part.

251 4. Datasets

252 As mentioned before in the IR/thermal object detection the available public datasets are
253 quite limited compared to their counter-part visual object detection datasets. In [7] where
254 a thorough research has been performed on the availability of such datasets, from a re-
255 ported 27 works on the field, 18 use a self-compiled dataset for their research and 2 did
256 not report their dataset. In summary 20 out of 27 works (over 74%) wouldn't utilize any
257 public dataset. This fact proves the lack of a universally accepted well-established public
258 dataset which would operate as benchmark for result reporting as is the case of Coco for
259 visual object detection. As it is obvious, this is a huge disadvantage for comparing works
260 and promoting innovation in the field. Possibly, the best known datasets in this field are
261 KAIST and FLIR-ADAS multispectral datasets. KAIST contains over 95k color-thermal
262 image pairs with resolution 640x480 but only 3 classes involving people are annotated:
263 person, people, cyclist. All other objects are not annotated and in order to utilize this
264 dataset a re-annotation is required.

265 For the purposes of this work 4 different datasets were utilised: FLIR-ADAS, HIT-UAV
266 [55], Corsican Fire Dataset [56] and Flame Dataset [57]. As mentioned before we have in-
267 cluded only the object which are relevant to the surveillance task and ignored all other
268 objects. Additionally, we have thoroughly examined the images provided to annotate
269 object instances we are interested in but were not originally annotated (as for example
270 fire instances).

271 FLIR-ADAS on the other hand provide annotations for 16 classes of interest: 15 specific
272 ones and 1 collective class for the remaining objects not belonging to any other class.
273 More specifically the classes are Person, Bike, Car, Motorcycle, Bus, Train, Truck, Traffic
274 light, Fire Hydrant, Street Sign, Dog, Skateboard, Stroller, Scooter and Other Vehicle. Of
275 those, the first 5 and Truck were included in the final dataset being utilized in this work.
276 The perspective under which the images were captured is from a moving car since the
277 dataset's initial purpose is for autonomous driving.

278 HIT-UAV is a high-altitude thermal dataset targeted at object detection. It comprises of
279 2,898 thermal images captured from UAV perspective in various scenarios, such as
280 schools, parking lots, roads, and playgrounds. It contains 5 classes: 3 specific ones, 1 col-
281 lective for the remaining vehicles and one labeled Don't Care. The classes are Car, Person,
282 Bicycle, Other Vehicle and Don't Care. For the purpose of the surveillance task the first 3
283 classes were selected.

284 In Table 1 the exact classes used from each dataset along with the actual object instances
285 included in the dataset are presented. The last column provided information for the ac-
286 cumulated dataset which was utilized for the training of the models. As it can observed
287 there are 7 classes included in the final compiled version. Nevertheless, the dataset is
288 quite unbalanced with 2 classes dominating the dataset, Person and Car, and accounting

for nearly 90% of all instances. The latter distribution has an impact on the ability of the model to predict certain classes.

Table 1. Number of classes in Datasets used.

Class	Dataset				
	FLIR-ADAS [8]	HIT-UAV [55]	Corsican fire [56]	Flame [57]	Combined
Person	✓(50478)	✓ (12312)	* (1107)	* (94)	63991 (39.0%)
Car	✓(73623)	✓ (7311)	* (147)	n/a	81081 (49.4%)
Bike	✓(7237)	✓ (4980)	n/a	n/a	12217 (7.4%)
Motorcycle	✓(1116)	n/a	n/a	n/a	1116 (0.7%)
Bus	✓(2245)	n/a	n/a	n/a	2245 (1.4%)
Train	× (5)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Truck	✓(829)	n/a	n/a	n/a	829 (0.5%)
Traffic light	× (16198)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Fire Hydrant	× (1095)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Street Sign	× (20770)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Dog	× (4)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Deer	× (8)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Skateboard	× (29)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Stroller	× (15)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Scooter	× (15)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Other Vehicle	× (1373)	× (148)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Don't Care	n/a	× (148)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Fire	n/a	n/a	✓(1021)	✓(1689)	2710 (1.7%)
Sum	135528	24603	2275	1783	164189

Regarding the symbols used in Table 1: ✓ means class was found in the original dataset and also in the final annotation. × the class was included in the original dataset but was excluded from the dataset utilized in this work. n/a (not available) means the class is not present in the dataset at all and * annotation for this class was missing in the original but added to the final dataset. (xxx) represents the number of object instances inside the dataset.

Corsican Fire Dataset is a dataset which focuses on fire detection. It contains both visual and near-infrared images and also provides segmentation masks. It focuses on outdoor fire instances and aims at providing a fire evolving dataset to promote the scientific research in the field. In total 640 infrared images were obtained to be included in the conducted experiments in this paper. It worth noting that the dataset contains a little more visual than infra-red images.

Flame Dataset is a multi-spectral datasets which focuses on external fire detection. It contains both visual and thermal videos of the fires. We have selected a video of the collection which contains thermal video footage, extracted the images every 180 frames and manually annotated the Fire and Person instances in the frames. A total of 742 frames was acquired, of which 581 frames contained Fire instances and were kept in the dataset.

The type of classes we chose the model to be trained on, are based on the ones which reveal human presence or activity [58]. For thermal object detection these include person figures and various vehicle types (Car, Truck, Bus, Motorcycle, Bicycle). Additionally, as stated, from the natural disasters list [58] we have also included fire instances as a crucial yet detectable threat which can expand the system practical use.

The 4 datasets present different qualities and offer a more complete figure of the detecting ability for the models under examination. The larger number of instances is contained

315 in the FLIR-ADAS dataset by a large margin. This dataset is the most challenging one, as
316 it can be seen by comparing the results in the three result Tables. As regards the dataset
317 split, when there was available an official data split it was utilized in the experiments.
318 This was the case for FLIR-ADAS and HIT-UAV datasets. Regarding the Flame v1 da-
319 taset the adopted methodology involved splitting the dataset in a 90%-10% train-
320 ing-validation set but keeping the first roughly 10% of the video to minimize the de-
321 pendency of the two sets. Obviously, there is a connection between the two sets but it
322 seems as a safer choice for evaluating the performance of the model. Finally, for the Cor-
323 sican Fire a random 90%-10% split was also applied to create the two sets.

324 5. Results

325 In this section we summarize the experiments and the results deduced by them. In
326 the aspect of this work an extended series of experiments have been conducted in order
327 to evaluate the performance of efficient state-of-the-art object detection models and more
328 specifically Yolov8, Yolov11 and RT-DETR v2 while being operating in IR/thermal spec-
329 trum. The experiments included both effectiveness as well efficiency metrics. This way, a
330 more comprehensive view of the models under inspection is provided and safer conclu-
331 sion can be extracted.

332 The lack of a large benchmark dataset has limited the options for providing results
333 easily comparable to other works. For this reason, we opted for a compiled dataset from 4
334 distinct public datasets. We have included the results in each dataset separately along
335 with the results in the compiled dataset. This way it is easier to evaluate the performance
336 of each model for the various parameters being utilised in each case. Although all da-
337 tasetes contain images in the IR spectrum they exhibit different behaviour and do not co-
338 incide in their best performance for the same set of parameters.

340 5.1. Training parameters and process

341
342 The parameters utilised during the conduction of experiments were kept to the de-
343 fault ones if not stated otherwise. More specifically, Yolov8 and Yolov11 shared the same
344 parameters which include Adam for the first 10000 iterations and SGD [59] with mo-
345 mentum for the rest iterations as optimizer with base learning rate set to 0.01, base weight
346 decay equal to 0.0005, momentum equal to 0.937, a linear learning rate schedule, certain
347 warm-up iterations and an exponential moving average (EMA) decay set to 0.9999.

348 RT-Detr v2 on the other hand, utilizes Res-Net [60] as its backbone which is pre-
349 trained in ImageNet [61]. Its optimizer is AdamW [62] with a fixed batch size of 3 (which
350 provided the best results) and an EMA is applied with $\text{ema_decay} = 0.9999$. For the op-
351 tional discrete sampling, an initial pre-training $6\times$ with the `grid_sample` operator is ap-
352 plied followed by fine-tuning $1\times$ with the `discrete_sample` operator. For scale-adaptive
353 parameters the learning rate is set to $1e-4$ and $5e-5$ for the backbones (ResNet18 and
354 ResNet34 respectively) while for the detection branch it is set for both models to $1e-4$.

355 Regarding the augmentation applied to the training phase, both models elaborated
356 extensive augmentation techniques in order to improve the models' robustness and
357 generalization ability. On one hand Yolov8 and Yolov11 shared the same techniques
358 which included color space alteration as well as geometric ones. Color space augmen-
359 tation included random values in the HSV channels of the image and color swaps in the
360 RGB space while the geometric ones refer to random rotation (by 90 degrees to fit the
361 image in its rectangle initial shape), translation of the whole image, scaling of the image
362 (either zooming in or out), shear translation, perspective transformation, flip up-down
363 and left-right, a mosaic new image compiled of 4 independent images, a mixup of 2 im-
364 ages (a blending of two images onto each other) and finally a compilation of a cut corner

of an image and the replacement of this part from a different image. On the other hand RT-Detr v2 utilizes random erasing a part of the image, random lighting of the image, apply random distortion including hue, saturation, contrast, brightness and color channel swap, resize the image, randomly add canvas around the image, random cropping, randomly cut a portion of an image and replace it with that of another image, apply blending of 2 images, random shift of an image and finally mosaic of 4 images. The most interesting part is that RT-Detr v2 applies a dynamic augmentation approach for the training, which means it switches off some of the augmentations for the final epochs of training.

Yolov8 and Yolov11 have been trained for 100 epochs in each experiment, while their counterpart RT-Detr v2 for 120 epochs following the setup provided by the developers of the respective models. The batch size for each experiment was set to the maximum allowed value for Yolos while for the transformer after experimentation it was kept fixed to 3 because the best performance was acquired using this parameter. The image resolution acquired 4 distinct values (as presented in the results Tables) utilised for both training and evaluation which are 640, 768, 896 and 1024. The model variation being chosen represent variations which typically present detection ability while maintaining their resources requirement to modest levels. As has been confirmed by the results, effectiveness of the models typically is diminishes after a certain input image size. The training and evaluation was conducted in a GeForce RTX 3080 (10 GB) and a NVIDIA RTX 4090 (24 GB). The efficiency evaluation was specifically measured in the less efficient card (RTX 3080) to get a minimal efficiency metric.

5.2. Models' efficiency

The efficiency results are presented in Table 2 where it can be seen how each model perform on this field in regards with other parameter like the image resolution and the model variation. Simply by comparing the speed of the models in inference mode, the faster one was Yolov8 followed by RT-Detr v2 and Yolov11 being the least efficient. The evaluation was performed on a modest GPU card, a GeForce RTX 3080 and it must be noted that all architectures achieved real-time performances (above 25 fps) for the models examined. Training was performed on a more powerful machine possessing a GeForce RTX 3090 card. More specifically, the models chosen to participate in this evaluation tests were the most efficient ones with the exception of nano variations which was skipped for both Yolov8 and Yolov11. Thus, the variations participated in the experiments were the small and medium ones for the Yolo candidates and r18vd and r34vd for the Transformer candidate. Although the best single processing time is achieved by Yolov8, this trend does not seem to be consistent. On the contrary, the analysis of the overall performance of each architecture reveals a more complex pattern for the speed of each model. As mentioned already, the faster model is Yolov8, yet its efficiency is highly impacted by the image resolution. For example in FLIR-ADAS when utilizing the small variation it achieves a fps 80 for the smallest resolution 640x640 but drops to 42 for the largest 1024x1024. This is a reduction of 47.5% which seems impressive. On the other hand RT-DETRv2 achieves a speed of 73 fps for the 640x640 resolution but achieves 54 fps for the 1024x1024 input images (a reduction of 26.0%) with the latter performance being much higher than the Yolov8's counterpart. Yolov11 which shares a lot of components with the Yolov8 architecture operates in a similar fashion and presents a drop of 46.4% (from 56 to 30 fps) between the smallest and largest image resolution inputs. Thus, the conclusion is that the efficiency of each model highly depends on the image resolution and the architecture used.

Another interesting fact is the way each model is affected by the increase of the image resolution. Yolos exhibit similar pattern regarding their performance as greater images are being utilised: their processing speed is decreased relatively fast. The fastest model is Yolov8 for the small variation and 640 image resolution, but when the image utilised increases to 1024 pixels the speed is dropped to almost half: from 80 to 42 fps. Yolov11 is least efficient model with best processing time at 56 fps for the smaller model in 640 pixel analysis which drops to 35 when 1024 pixel images are inserted in the system. This trend is even increased if the more powerful variation is utilised, the medium one. In this case the speed varies from 56 to 30 fps for Yolov8 and 48 to 25 fps for the Yolov11 model. On the contrary, RT-Detr v2 while being the second fastest model with 73 fps in the smallest resolution (640x640) it scales more smoothly when 1024 pixel images are thrown to the model which can be processed at 54 fps (almost as the fastest performance of Yolov11). So, as a conclusion, RT-Detr can maintain its processing time more stable as the input image fluctuates which is a huge advantage over Yolos.

Table 2. Efficiency results of the models.

model	variation	image resolution	Fps	parameters (M)	GFlops
Yolov8	small	640x640	80	11.1	28.8
		768x768	66	11.1	41.5
		896x896	51	11.1	56.5
		1024x1024	42	11.1	73.8
	medium	640x640	56	25.9	79.3
		768x768	45	25.9	114.2
		896x896	37	25.9	155.5
		1024x1024	30	25.9	203.1
Yolo11	small	640x640	56	9.4	21.7
		768x768	48	9.4	31.3
		896x896	43	9.4	42.6
		1024x1024	35	9.4	55.6
	medium	640x640	48	20.1	68.5
		768x768	38	20.1	98.7
		896x896	31	20.1	134.3
		1024x1024	25	20.1	175.4
RT-Detr v2	r18	640x640	73	20.0	61.1
		768x768	63	20.0	87.1
		896x896	58	20.0	117.8
		1024x1024	54	20.0	153.4
	r34	640x640	57	31.3	93.2
		768x768	48	31.3	132.9
		896x896	44	31.3	180.0
		1024x1024	40	31.3	234.3

5.3. Model's effectiveness

The results regarding the performance of each model for the various image resolutions is presented in Table 5. As it can be seen from Table 2 the goal of providing re-

al-time performance is matched for all model examined but with big differences between model performances. Thus, this factor should be taken into consideration when impacting performance. Regarding the actual mAP achieved, the differences observed in Table 5 are less impressive. The best performance was achieved by Yolov8 at 0.544, followed closely by Yolov11 at 0.541 and finally RT-Detr at 0.517. Its counterpart mAP0.50 gave similar results with Yolov8 achieving 0.781, Yolov11 0.780 and RT-Detr 0.759 and the differences is even smaller. The individual precision in each dataset gave more diverse outcomes. More specifically, in FLIR-ADAS and Corsican Yolov8 took the first place and in HIT-UAV and Flame Yolov11 received the best performance.

Table 3. Per class mAP performance of the models.

Model	All	Car	Person	Truck	Motorcycle	Bus	Bicycle	Fire
Yolov8	0.543	0.693	0.557	0.283	0.443	0.531	0.584	0.707
Yolo11	0.541	0.703	0.566	0.214	0.479	0.532	0.587	0.702
RT-Detr	0.517	0.674	0.536	0.189	0.443	0.502	0.552	0.720

At first glance the difference in the best mAP or mAP0.5 for each model is minimal, especially between the two Yolos which has a difference of 0.002. On a second analysis layer, when the processing ability of each model is included we can observe that Yolov8 can process 37 fps, Yolov11 25 frames and RT-Detr 40 frames at the same time. As it can be observed the order is reversed in the processing speed with the first place going to RT-Detr. Thus, in cases where the most important aspect is delivering a quick detection system the inclusion of RT-Detr might be the best option.

Attempting a more scrutinised analysis per class, we present the best mAP performance for each model and its performance over each class in Table 3. First of all, as it is expected the average precision is quite diverse for specific classes. The lowest performing classes is the Truck one, which can be attributed to low instance number as well as visual proximity with the Bus class especially in the thermal spectrum (in the visual one there is also the advantage of clearer images and color information). To further elaborate for the misclassification of each class a Confusion Matrix has been produced, displayed in Figure 1. The model which was selected to produce the Confusion Matrix is the best performing one, Yolov8 medium at 896 image resolution. It can be seen that indeed the majority of the Truck objects belong to the Bus class, followed by the Car class. The threshold for validating a detection is set to 0.02 (under this threshold the detection is dismissed) and the threshold for assigning to a ground truth bounding box is IoU of 0.5 (IoU value less than considers this specific detection to be false positive). An interesting part is that Yolov11 had the most first places with 5 but Yolov8 had the best overall mAP. Yolov8 and RT-Detr had one first place each. As it is obvious from the classes, at least some of them can be combined to improve performance.

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Figure 1. Confusion Matrix of the detected objects vs the actual objects. The model utilized is the best performing Yolov8 896 model.

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In order to mitigate the imbalance of the dataset we have attempted certain methods to examine if any of them could improve the performance in the mis-performing classes as well to the overall model performance. In the following Table, Table 4, results of applying certain mitigation methods are presented. The best performing model is chosen, Yolov8, to apply the methods on. Yolov8 medium at 896 image resolution achieves 0.543 mAP and Truck 0.283 AP. None of the methods achieves higher mAP, with only the weighted classes, in which the Truck was assigned a weight of 20 while all other classes had 1 achieved the same mAP. Nevertheless, even in this case the Truck AP was less than the original one 0.233 vs 0.283. Thus, we couldn't encounter any fruitful mitigation method for the poor performance of the Truck class.

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Table 4. Weighted training for the Yolov8 model.

Model	All	Car	Person	Truck	Motorcycle	Bus	Bicycle	Fire
Yolov8m 896	0.543	0.693	0.557	0.283	0.443	0.531	0.584	0.707
Yolov8m 1024	0.538	0.701	0.564	0.229	0.460	0.521	0.583	0.711
Yolov8m weighted data-loader 896	0.526	0.677	0.544	0.193	0.472	0.521	0.573	0.703
Yolov8m weighted data-loader 1024	0.519	0.689	0.552	0.218	0.407	0.507	0.564	0.700
Yolov8m weighted classes Truckx20	0.543	0.697	0.558	0.233	0.465	0.534	0.583	0.732

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Finally, analysing the per individual dataset performance we observe a similar trend with the combined dataset performance. Of the four datasets, two first places are taken by Yolov8 and two by Yolov11 for mAP metric. When mAP50 is utilised as metric the

490 general image does not change since again the top spots are split between the two Yolos.
 491 As a conclusion, Yolos share a similar partner, and thus, their performance is quite close
 492 in all four datasets while RT-Detr is somehow deviating from this pattern.

493 The comparison between CNN based detectors (Yolovs) and transformer ones
 494 (RT-Detr v2) indicated a superiority of the former which might seem counter intuitive.
 495 We suspect this behavior to be boosted by the small dataset size since transformers tend
 496 to be more reliable to large dataset availability [63]. Since, the dataset being utilized for
 497 this paper are relatively small, this could be the reason for performing worse than the
 498 CNN based counter-parts. A solution for this drawback is to take advantage of the ability
 499 of the transformers to extract generic features from their (typically large) training set and
 500 later be successfully fine-tuned in a smaller dataset. This approach often is proven fruit-
 501 ful because the features transformers learn tend to be generic, and thus, highly robust to
 502 transfer to different tasks [64].

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 504 In the following Figures detection examples are presented to visualize the detection
 505 ability of the models. In each example only the best model's output is depicted in each
 506 dataset (Yolov8 or Yolov11).

(a)

(b)

507 **Figure 2.** Detection example from FLIR-ADAS dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original image from
 508 the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.

(a)

(b)

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 510 **Figure 3.** Detection example from HIT-UAV dataset using Yolov11. (a) The original image from the
 511 dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.

(a)

(b)

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Figure 4. Detection example from Corsican Fire dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.

(a)

(b)

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Figure 5. Detection example from Flame dataset using Yolov11. (a) The original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.

(a)

(b)

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Figure 6. Detection example containing errors from FLIR-ADAS dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes. The car (van) is detected as 2 distinct instances

(a)

(b)

521 **Figure 7.** Detection example containing errors from FLIR-ADAS dataset using YOLOv8. (a) The
 522 original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding
 523 boxes. A false positive bike being detected.

(a)

(b)

524 **Figure 8.** Detection example containing errors from HIT-UAV dataset using YOLOv8. (a) The origi-
 525 nal image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.
 526 A car is not being detected (false negative).

(a)

(b)

527 **Figure 9.** Detection example containing errors from HIT-UAV dataset using YOLOv8. (a) The origi-
 528 nal image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes.
 529 A car is not being detected (false negative).

530 **Figure 10.** Detection example containing errors from Flame v1 dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes. A non-existent fire instance is being detected (false positive).
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533 **Figure 11.** Detection example containing errors from Corsican Fire dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original image from the dataset; (b) The detected objects being annotated as overlaid bounding boxes. A fire instance is being detected twice (2 false negatives).
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537 Table 5. Effectiveness results of the models (mAP/mAP⁵⁰).

model	variation	image resol.	FLIR-ADAS v2	HIT-UAV	Corsican	Flame	Combined
Yolov8	small	640	0.429/0.647	0.642/0.946	0.805/0.970	0.579/0.866	0.501/0.749
		768	0.435/0.665	0.646/0.946	0.827/0.974	0.614/0.901	0.509/0.751
		896	0.454/0.676	0.650/0.948	0.826/0.973	0.585/0.873	0.513/0.757
		1024	0.452/0.667	0.649/0.949	0.822/0.974	0.586/0.870	0.518/0.753
	medium	640x640	0.460/0.679	0.643/0.947	0.826/0.979	0.604/0.878	0.525/0.762
		768x768	0.461/0.680	0.645/0.944	0.823/0.972	0.624/0.872	0.532/0.765
		896x896	0.475/0.692	0.653/0.948	0.811/0.969	0.623/0.907	0.543/0.781
		1024x1024	0.470/0.689	0.653/0.947	0.820/0.965	0.597/0.849	0.538/0.774
Yolo11	small	640x640	0.425/0.664	0.642/0.948	0.819/0.969	0.606/0.926	0.529/0.769
		768x768	0.437/0.673	0.651/0.946	0.808/0.974	0.600/0.891	0.520/0.757

		896x896	0.447/0.668	0.652/0.950	0.820/0.974	0.598/0.901	0.514/0.754
		1024x1024	0.448/0.670	0.653/0.949	0.813/0.965	0.591/0.886	0.499/0.740
	medium	640x640	0.451/0.681	0.649/0.947	0.817/0.970	0.630/0.903	0.525/0.770
		768x768	0.463/0.680	0.653/0.953	0.821/0.974	0.628/0.902	0.539/0.772
		896x896	0.470/0.689	0.657/0.950	0.819/0.969	0.622/0.885	0.538/0.773
		1024x1024	0.468/0.684	0.653/0.953	0.818/0.972	0.608/0.885	0.541/0.773
	r18	640x640	0.425/0.648	0.622/0.948	0.808/0.947	0.587/0.915	0.494/0.739
		768x768	0.437/0.653	0.627/0.945	0.803/0.953	0.605/0.916	0.509/0.750
		896x896	0.454/0.676	0.629/0.947	0.799/0.961	0.595/0.882	0.516/0.758
		1024x1024	0.446/0.661	0.632/0.947	0.803/0.965	0.604/0.911	0.503/0.735
RT-Detr v2	r34	640x640	0.450/0.684	0.625/0.950	0.779/0.950	0.630/0.902	0.502/0.759
		768x768	0.440/0.682	0.620/0.949	0.789/0.954	0.605/0.871	0.509/0.752
		896x896	0.445/0.667	0.608/0.938	0.790/0.953	0.601/0.879	0.517/0.768
		1024x1024	0.445/0.668	0.594/0.926	0.791/0.953	0.651/0.888	0.514/0.755

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To further examine the models' generalization ability we have selected a subset of SMOD multi-modal dataset [65]. This dataset contains images from 4 modalities, RGB, fir (far IR), mir (middle IR) and nir (Near IR). We have selected the first 500 images and perform inference on this subset. The 4 modalities does not contain images in the same resolution and most importantly field of view which might have an impact on the model's performance. It is obvious that RGB and fir have the larger field of view, while mir and nir cover much smaller area. Another observation is that nir is visually closer to the visual spectrum than to fir. This explains the poor performance of our model on it, since our training did not contain any image from the visual spectrum (although Corsican dataset is captured in nir band). The following Figures, Figure 12 and 13, contain examples of this inference on SMOD. As a conclusion of this inference experiment, we can infer that:

a) The model's modality is crucial for its detection ability (nir modality performs worse than the fir one)

b) The difference in modality can cause false positives (in the first nir image the traffic light is detected as fire instance) of false negatives.

c) To provide the model with robust generalized detection abilities a diverse and possibly multi-modal thermal dataset would be beneficiary.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

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Figure 12. Detection example from SMOD dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original RGB image (shown for object demonstration); (b) The detected objects to the nir image as overlay bounding boxes; (c) The detected objects to the mir image as overlay bounding boxes; (d) The detected objects to the fir image as overlay bounding boxes.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. Detection example from SMOD dataset using Yolov8. (a) The original RGB image (shown for object demonstration); (b) The detected objects to the nir image as overlay bounding boxes; (c) The detected objects to the mir image as overlay bounding boxes; (d) The detected objects to the fir image as overlay bounding boxes.

6. Conclusions

In this work a comprehensive research over the ability of IR/thermal object detection models to fulfill their role as backbone for IR/thermal security detection system has been performed. The models included to participate were state-of-the-art examples and were chosen for their stellar performance. Additionally, a second requirement for the models was their efficiency; every model examined can provide a real-time processing speed for image resolutions up to 1024 pixels even when examined in middle-end GPU cards.

For the research activity, a compilation of thermal/IR publicly available datasets has been utilized. The compiled dataset underwent filtering for the irrelevant classes –which were ruled out– and manual annotation for the object instances present but not annotated. This led to an unbalanced dataset with which we attempted to cover the requirement for detections. The performance of each model has provided efficient operation yet their performance in detection ability was lower than expected with better mAP reaching 0.544. This fact is mainly attributed to the lack of a larger dataset, which would cover more diverse object instances, capturing angles and distances. Through the experiments, it has been shown that larger image resolution or model power does not guarantee better overall performance. The latter fact in combination with the decrease in model efficiency as its processing power increases, tends to promote medium models and resolutions as the best options. Nevertheless, this works provided evidence that a security system can benefit by incorporating IR/thermal detection in its set of tools to further improve its detection ability and armor it against undetected threats.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

IR	Infra-red
RGB	Red Green Blue
RCNN	Region-based Convolutional Neural Network
GB	Giga Bytes
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HSV	Hue Saturation Value

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